

DECENTRALIZED PROFESSIONAL PASSPORT EMPOWERING INDEPENDENT WORK

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Abstract

Keywords:

1. Introduction

TiiQu is a blockchain based platform that uses the immutability and verifiable source of data qualities inherent to blockchains to create a digital “passport”, which can be relied on as proof of an individual’s professional trustworthiness, identity, qualifications, certifications, memberships, previous work experience, performance metrics and education. The platform provides a transparent infrastructure and easy to author “smart contracts” enforcing conditions and payment of collaboration agreements at a fraction of time and costs currently associated with verification, hiring and payments

2. Aim

Facilitate global collaboration without middlemen in a globalized flexible and meritocratic labour market

TiiQu replaces the former subjective assessment of job candidates on part of HR managers and head-hunters with the TQ (trust quotient), a score comprised of all digitally verified claims collected in the professional passport.

The TQ mitigates the subjectivity of reputational elements with objective data and since each claim is certified by third parties on -chain, the TQ can be said a tamper-proof objective evaluation of an individual’s trustability. It reduces arbitrariness in professional assessments and creates a level playing field for applicants, neutral to all biases of gender, ethnicity, religion, and class.

3. Material and methods

The Trust Quotient (TQ) is the algorithmically derived value representing an individual’s objective trustworthiness relative to their peers and based on proofs provided by the individual. The TQ quantifies trust based on proofs relating to an individual’s identity, reputation, veracity and performance. By establishing multiple sources for each of the above criteria the TQ is able to robustly quantify the base components of trust.

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Source weighting allows for a TQ rating to favour sources over others and applies to all criteria with the exception of veracity. With respect to veracity, all proven claims are equal and proving a claim impacts on an individual's TQ rating, but the nature of the claim doesn't impact on an individual's TQ rating.

Trustworthiness is handled separately from suitability questions. Only verification of expertise can have an impact on the TQ. But in this context, only the fact of the proven claim counts and not the quality of the claim itself. Furthermore, an expert's TQ will neither depend on the number of achieved certifications or experienced workfields nor on the range of his expertise

4. Results

The TiiQu algorithm will evolve over time and with the gathered experience from integrating new kinds of experts. Because of this, the fairness in our system will be based on dynamically computed trust quotients from present values, ranges and weights. Every time we adapt the algorithm, each TiiQu member will have the same conditions. The Algorithm will be tested and progressively adapted starting from the Alpha test.

Author biography

Laura Degiovanni Serial entrepreneur building innovative business models from scratch and developing multi-channel businesses on EMEA markets. Laura experienced work from different perspectives: employer, senior manager in a multinational group, consultant, coming to identify the need and design the scalable solution to efficiently integrate outsourced on-demand resources with internal workforce of organizations concurrently satisfying the growing demand for flexibility of the business world and the new approach to work of new generations looking for meaningful work and independence.